

Pricing and infrastructure fees in shaping cooperation in a model of high-speed rail and airline competition ^{*}

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Abstract

This paper studies the effects of cooperation in a hub-and-spoke network with high-speed rail and airline competition. The distinctive elements of our analysis are the consideration of: i) per-passenger airport and rail infrastructure fees; ii) mixed bundling pricing by partners, and iii) an airline duopoly in the international market. We show that partners fix the cheapest bundle price of the combined trip, that non-allied operators respond by decreasing the prices per link, and that connecting traffic increases. Per-passenger fees significantly affect the price differences following cooperation. An empirical application confirms that it is privately profitable and that welfare gains are in the range of 0.8-2.2%; these can be higher for lower fees or lower cross-price elasticity between modes.

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1 Introduction

The growth of high speed rail (HSR) networks in developed countries has brought major changes in the supply of interurban transportation. With increased train speed, HSR has indeed become a competitor of air transport (Rothengatter, 2011), especially for short-to-medium haul passenger markets, where the rail option is better in terms of check in/out times, punctuality, frequency of service and the proximity to city centers. According to the Union Internationale des Chemins de Fer (2019), worldwide HSR lines reached 46,403 km in operation. The development of HSR services has produced a substitution effect; there has been an increase in the demand for rail transport and a traffic reallocation with regard to passenger volumes and market shares from air to rail transport (Behrens and Pels, 2012, Betancor and Jiménez, 2012, Bergantino et al., 2015). However, some railway infrastructure can also be seen as part of the air transport infrastructure (Givoni and Banister, 2006), which suggests demand complementarities between these two modes of transport. Although intermodal cooperation would involve wider choice and facilitate passenger mobility, it may distort competition in markets where both modes were former competitors.

We wish to explore the effects of cooperation in a setting where connecting passengers consider differentiated substitute bundles that are composed of complementary legs involving either air-air or air-HSR transport.¹ The distinctive elements of our analysis that adds to the received literature on airline-HSR cooperation are the consideration of: i) per-passenger airport and rail infrastructure

¹Examples of intermodal competition in which HSR has become a dominating substitute for airline travel include London-Paris, Frankfurt-Cologne, Madrid-Valencia, Beijing-Tianjin and Tokyo-Osaka. There are several examples of demand complementarities in airline-HSR cooperation in Europe. The AIRail service provided by Lufthansa and Deutsche Bahn allows intermodal passengers to use HSR services on the Frankfurt-Cologne route and then air services at Frankfurt airport. Thalys International offers air-and-rail combined trips between Brussels and Paris CDG and between Anvers and Amsterdam Schiphol. In the United States, Amtrak and United Airlines offer seamless service by HSR linking several East Coast cities and Newark International Airport. We also find a cooperation agreement between China Railway High-Speed and China Eastern Airlines at Shanghai International Airport.

fees in shaping prices, traffic and welfare; ii) partners taking into account that they fully control the price of one combination and partially control the price of some others, and iii) an airline duopoly in the international market.

The literature has studied the case of airline-HSR competition, both theoretically and empirically (see Section 2 for a review). However, it is only recently that attention has been devoted to the analysis of modal substitutability and modal complementarity in a hub-and-spoke network. The few existing contributions include Socorro and Vicens (2013), Jiang and Zhang (2014), Xia and Zhang (2016), Jiang et al. (2017) and Avenali et al. (2018). These analyses examine the effects of air-HSR cooperation when modes are horizontally or vertically differentiated while considering various types of partnership. Despite their valuable conclusions, restrictive assumptions regarding the available transport alternatives are made in the competition and cooperation scenarios. Although Xia and Zhang (2016) and Avenali et al. (2018) contemplate all connections for connecting passengers, quantity competition is assumed; none of the above papers considers infrastructure per-passenger fees. Our paper contributes to this line of research by considering price competition, to effectively account for internalization of demand complementarity under cooperation while allowing for all transport combinations. Most importantly, our analysis looks at the effect of per-passenger fees that are different per use of each infrastructure. Besides, the calibration exercise allows us to quantify the effects of rail-air and air-air cooperation agreements.

A transport network is considered with two links connecting three cities by developing a formal model to investigate the effects of cooperation when air and HSR are substitutes in one of the links and complements for those passengers that make a combined trip including the two links. In the other link passengers can take an international flight with either of two airlines. Per-passenger fees, which are different as per infrastructure, are taken into account.² With competition, there are four prices, corresponding to each price set by the operators on each link. With cooperation, partners also set the price for their combined trip, the bundle price. We show that partners increase the prices per link for a

²For the sake of exposition we will refer to these fees as airport and rail fees, respectively.

high enough degree of product substitutability. Under rail-air cooperation, airport fees increase the rail component price relative to competition while the air component price decreases. However, under air-air cooperation, rail fees always reduce the price differences in partners component prices, while airport fees decrease price differences only for large enough product substitutability. Non-allied operators typically respond by decreasing the prices per link. Partners internalize the competition that arises when pricing their complementary links; the price for the bundle or combined trip is cheaper than the sum of prices before cooperation. Besides, the bundle price is cheaper than the combination offered by non-allied operators as well as the mix-and-match combinations (having an allied and a no-allied operator). Such price differences are found to be reduced with the rail fee under rail-air cooperation; however, rail fees have the opposite effect under air-air cooperation when we consider the combination offered by non-allied operators. Finally, connecting passengers are better off when the price decrease response of non-allied operators offsets the increase in the sum of link prices by partners.

The model is also calibrated for the Valencia(Spain)-Madrid(Spain)-New York network. We may subsequently simulate the effects of HSR-air cooperation and check any differences with airline cooperation. Simulations confirm the price effects predicted by the model. Cooperation basically results in notable consumer surplus gains for connecting passengers because the bundle price is significantly lower than the sum of link prices. However, cooperation triggers effects on prices in the rest of markets leading to a redistribution of consumer surplus across markets. Cooperation is certainly profitable for partner firms, and results in welfare gains in the range of 0.8-2.2% depending on the type of cooperation and the level of per-passenger fees. Air-air cooperation has a larger impact on alliance profits, connecting passengers surplus and welfare because air services respond more to price changes as compared to rail services. Each alliance type has different effects on HSR traffic; air-air cooperation reduces total HSR traffic but increases local traffic between Valencia and Madrid, while rail-air cooperation increases total traffic although the local one falls.

We also discuss that the rail-air agreement is more likely to be proposed as it generates a larger profits increase. However, it results in the lowest value of total passenger surplus thereby raising antitrust concerns. The robustness of our findings is checked by providing a sensitivity analysis for changes in per-passenger fees and for different values of the cross-price elasticity. Lowering per-passenger fees does not affect the relative effects induced by cooperation agreements; a 1% decrease in all fees results in passenger gains in all scenarios, the most important being under rail-air cooperation. Higher values of the cross-price elasticity leads to passenger and welfare losses under rail-air cooperation. In contrast, lower values give rise to larger percentage gains in passenger surplus, industry profits and welfare. Finally, the analysis is conducted for the case of a network carrier that competes with rail and with an international airline. Our setting features a monopolization effect leading to different results because cooperation involves a loss in passenger surplus (hence a matter of concern for authorities). Although the incentives to cooperate increase, welfare decreases under the rail-network carrier agreement while it slightly increases under the other cooperation agreement.

Section 2 considers the related literature. Section 3 describes the model. Three different subsections present the equilibrium prices under competition, under cooperation and offer some results. The model is calibrated in Section 4, where the effects of cooperation are simulated. It includes subsections devoted to sensitivity analysis and robustness. Section 5 concludes.

2 Related literature

The literature has usually considered air and rail transport as alternative modes in direct competition, and modes that are perceived as differentiated in the eyes of passengers.³ In addition to competition between modes, internal competition

³González-Savignat (2004) and Park and Ha (2006) find strong substitutability effects between air and rail services following the introduction of a high speed rail link in Spain and Korea, respectively, and conventional airlines may leave the market, as shown by Behrens and Pels (2012) in the London-Paris route. In a fairly rich game theoretic setting, Adler et al. (2010) compute equilibria (decision variables, profits of operators and welfare) with and without high-speed rail investments and conclude that European HSR networks should be encouraged. Other theoretical

may also be present either in air transport (because of airline competition in international routes or the emergence of Low Cost Carriers) or in rail transport (due to the introduction of on-track competition), which leads to lower fares, traffic redistribution away from incumbents that would lose traffic and passenger surplus gains.⁴

As suggested above, evidence exists that HSR can complement air service (Givoni and Banister, 2006, Clewlow et al., 2012). The empirical exercise by Albalade et al. (2015) for large European countries confirms that HSR and airlines compete directly with one another, but also give some evidence that HSR can provide feeding services to long-haul air services in hub airports. The reduction of air services at hub airports is generally greater than that at non-hub airports. Liu et al. (2019) find that increases in HSR connectivity or accessibility have the desired effects for China and Japan; hub airports experience significant total traffic gains when HSR intermodal linkage is available –see Zhang et al. (2019) for a survey on recent research on air-HSR competition. This research suggests the consideration of a richer setting that stresses both substitutability and complementarity while allowing for a proper investigation of airline-HSR cooperation.⁵

The number of analytical works that examine the impact of HSR-air cooperation in a network structure is scarce. Socorro and Vicens (2013) analyze the social and environmental effects of airline and HSR integration. They adopt a representative consumer approach to product differentiation and the airline and the HSR company maximize their joint profit when they are integrated; they can set a single fare for the whole interline trip. These authors show that integration is privately profitable for partners, beneficial for connecting passengers and detrimental for those in the HSR accessible market, yet the overall effect on welfare is ambiguous. In a similar network, Jiang and Zhang (2014) assume instead

contributions include Yang and Zhang (2012), Jiang and Zhang (2016) and D'Alfonso et al. (2015).

⁴See, for example, Ivaldi and Vibes (2008), Álvarez San-Jaime et al. (2015) and Bergantino et al. (2015).

⁵Representative papers on complementary airline alliances include Park (1997), Brueckner (2001), Bilotkach (2005) Park et al. (2001), and Flores-Fillol and Moner-Colonques (2007), to mention a few.

quantity competition. Their analysis finds analogous predictions to Socorro and Vicens (2013) - with horizontal product differentiation - and to Xia and Zhang (2016) - with vertical product differentiation - regarding the changes in traffic following intermodal cooperation; besides, Jiang and Zhang (2014) show that if the modal substitutability is high between HSR and airlines, then hub capacity plays an important role in assessing the welfare impact. The contribution by Jiang et al. (2017) studies various partnership agreements, which are endogenous, in a connecting market involving a domestic and an international leg. Quantity competition is assumed and costly investments can be made to increase the cooperation levels, which eventually decrease the full price of the trip. Results are shown to depend on the pre-investment rail-air service quality; an exclusive domestic rail-air agreement appears when such cost is large enough as compared with the quality of air-air service although a single domestic agreement is never optimal. Xia and Zhang (2017) take a vertical differentiation approach in a transport network structure to study the effects of reducing rail-air connecting time. Their numerical analysis discloses that it is beneficial for consumers, and that social welfare is enhanced when the hub airport is capacity constrained and the rail-air integration is not too costly. Finally, Avenali et al. (2018) also consider quantity competition in a network structure to examine the effects of a vertical (the HSR operator sells seats to the airline) and a horizontal (operators offer the combined rail-air service) agreement, which is costly. They identify conditions on the degree of hub congestion and modal substitutability for cooperation to improve consumers surplus and welfare.

Although the two alternative forms of cooperation we study consider similar strategic tools and raise connecting traffic, rail-air collaborations actually have some distinctive features as compared to air-air ones. Rail-air cooperation improves people's mobility, reduces the negative environmental impact of transportation, stimulates economic growth and improves spatial redistribution of traffic and economic development across regions (Zhang et al. 2019). Intermodal complementarities provided by HSR induce asymmetric impacts on airlines and

airports that imply, usually, traffic reallocation to more connected and with-HSR-access hubs; and reallocation to international airlines connecting cities that do not have HSR access. Such traffic reallocations can either mitigate congestion in hub airports (Jiang and Zhang, 2014, Kroes and Savelberg, 2019) or worsen it depending on the course and size of the traffic reallocations (Liu et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2018). Additionally, there are studies justifying that the replacement of the reduction of air passenger by HSR passenger would reduce total CO2 emissions (Wang et al., 2019), while others are not so conclusive (D'Alfonso et al. 2015 and 2016). Also, the rail-air collaboration is more difficult to be effective. The possibility that HSR can have direct access to the airport, or the existence of systems that favor the interchange of luggage between HSR and airlines will be key aspects to facilitate the collaboration between HSR and airlines.

3 The model

A transportation network with three nodes is considered, as illustrated in Figure 1, and identifies three markets. The local (short) market AH is served by a local airline and by a HSR operator. The international (long) market HB is supplied by two airlines. Finally, the connecting market AB , where there is no direct service and passengers must take a combined trip.⁶ Note that connecting passengers can make four different combinations and two of them involve both air and rail transport.

The utility functions of a representative passenger in the local AH market, in the international HB market and in the connecting AB market are, respectively,

⁶As pointed out by the reviewers, it might be more appropriate to name the market served by the HSR operator as the short market and the one served by the two airlines as the long market. In that way, notation would allow the HSR to also operate international routes. The terminology local and international is maintained for the sake of the calibration example presented below.

Figure 1: Transportation network.

given by

$$U_l = a_l(q_t + q_a) - \frac{b}{2}(q_t^2 + q_a^2) - d_l q_t q_a, \quad (1)$$

$$U_i = a_i(q_{i1} + q_{i2}) - \frac{b}{2}(q_{i1}^2 + q_{i2}^2) - d_i q_{i1} q_{i2}, \quad (2)$$

$$U_c = a_c(x_{t1} + x_{t2} + x_{a1} + x_{a2}) - \frac{b}{2}(x_{t1}^2 + x_{t2}^2 + x_{a1}^2 + x_{a2}^2) - d_c(x_{t1}x_{t2} + x_{t1}x_{a1} + x_{t1}x_{a2} + x_{t2}x_{a1} + x_{t2}x_{a2} + x_{a1}x_{a2}), \quad (3)$$

where q_t and q_a denote the number of passengers by HSR and by the domestic airline, respectively. Similarly, q_{i1} and q_{i2} stand for the number of passengers of airlines 1 and 2 in the international market. Finally, x_{t1} denotes passenger traffic that takes the HSR in link AH and airline 1 in link HB , with obvious notation for the other three possible combinations. Constants a_l , a_i and a_c are positive and represent the maximum willingness to pay for travelling in the local (subscript l), international (i) and connecting (c) markets, respectively. It is also assumed that $b > d_l, d_i, d_c > 0$, and services become less differentiated as d 's tend to b .

Maximization of the utility functions subject to the budget constraints yields a system of inverse demand functions. The demand functions that correspond to the three markets are the following:

i) Local market demand system, *AH* market:

$$q_t(p_t, p_a) = \alpha_l - \beta_l p_t + \gamma_l p_a, \quad (4)$$

$$q_a(p_t, p_a) = \alpha_l - \beta_l p_a + \gamma_l p_t, \quad (5)$$

so that p_t and p_a are the price of an *AH* trip by train and by air, respectively.

ii) International market demand system, *HB* market:

$$q_{i1}(p_{i1}, p_{i2}) = \alpha_i - \beta_i p_{i1} + \gamma_i p_{i2}, \quad (6)$$

$$q_{i2}(p_{i1}, p_{i2}) = \alpha_i - \beta_i p_{i2} + \gamma_i p_{i1}, \quad (7)$$

where p_{i1} and p_{i2} are the price of an *HB* trip by airline 1 and airline 2, respectively.

iii) Connecting market demand system, *AB* market:

$$x_{t1}(s_{t1}, s_{t2}, s_{a1}, s_{a2}) = \alpha_c - \beta_c s_{t1} + \gamma_c \sum_{\forall l \neq t1} s_l, \quad (8)$$

$$x_{t2}(s_{t1}, s_{t2}, s_{a1}, s_{a2}) = \alpha_c - \beta_c s_{t2} + \gamma_c \sum_{\forall l \neq t2} s_l, \quad (9)$$

$$x_{a1}(s_{t1}, s_{t2}, s_{a1}, s_{a2}) = \alpha_c - \beta_c s_{a1} + \gamma_c \sum_{\forall l \neq a1} s_l, \quad (10)$$

$$x_{a2}(s_{t1}, s_{t2}, s_{a1}, s_{a2}) = \alpha_c - \beta_c s_{a2} + \gamma_c \sum_{\forall l \neq a2} s_l, \quad (11)$$

where x_{t1} passengers pay p_t in link *AH* and p_{i1} in link *HB*. Total price $s_{t1} = p_t + p_{i1}$ is inversely related to x_{t1} and positively related with the total price of the other three combinations $s_{t2} = p_t + p_{i2}$, $s_{a1} = p_a + p_{i1}$, and $s_{a2} = p_a + p_{i2}$, because combinations are substitutes to one another in the eyes of connecting passengers. A similar logic applies to demands x_{t2} , x_{a1} and x_{a2} . Further note that, $\alpha_k = \frac{(b-d_k)a_k}{b^2-d_k^2}$; $\beta_k = \frac{b}{b^2-d_k^2}$ and $\gamma_k = \frac{d_k}{b^2-d_k^2}$ for $k = l, i$. While $\alpha_c = \frac{(b-d_c)a_c}{(b-d_c)(b+3d_c)}$; $\beta_c = \frac{b+2d_c}{(b-d_c)(b+3d_c)}$ and $\gamma_c = \frac{d_c}{(b-d_c)(b+3d_c)}$.

With regard to costs, c_t and c_a denote the marginal (operating) cost per passenger by train and air, respectively. Finally, airlines are charged per-passenger fees per use of infrastructure incurred both at the origin and at the destination points; f_t is the per-passenger rail fee and f_A, f_B and f_H denote the per-passenger airport fee at airports *A, B* and *H*, respectively.

3.1 The equilibrium under competition

The rail operator and airline profits read as follows:

$$\pi_t = (p_t - c_t - 2f_t)(q_t + x_{t1} + x_{t2}), \quad (12)$$

$$\pi_a = (p_a - c_a - f_A - f_H)(q_a + x_{a1} + x_{a2}), \quad (13)$$

$$\pi_{i1} = (p_{i1} - c_a - f_B - f_H)(q_{i1} + x_{t1} + x_{a1}), \quad (14)$$

$$\pi_{i2} = (p_{i2} - c_a - f_B - f_H)(q_{i2} + x_{t2} + x_{a2}). \quad (15)$$

Operators choose simultaneously and independently the profit maximizing prices. Focusing on the First Order Conditions (FOC) of the HSR firm and the international airline 1 we have:

$$\frac{\partial \pi_t}{\partial p_t} = (q_t + x_{t1} + x_{t2}) + (p_t - c_t - 2f_t) \left(\frac{\partial q_t}{\partial p_t} + \frac{\partial x_{t1}}{\partial p_t} + \frac{\partial x_{t2}}{\partial p_t} \right) = 0, \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{i1}}{\partial p_{i1}} = (q_{i1} + x_{t1} + x_{a1}) + (p_{i1} - c_a - f_B - f_H) \left(\frac{\partial q_{i1}}{\partial p_{i1}} + \frac{\partial x_{t1}}{\partial p_{i1}} + \frac{\partial x_{a1}}{\partial p_{i1}} \right) = 0. \quad (17)$$

Noting that $\frac{\partial q_t}{\partial p_t} = -\beta_l$, $\frac{\partial q_{i1}}{\partial p_{i1}} = -\beta_i$ and $\frac{\partial x_{t1}}{\partial p_t} = \frac{\partial x_{t2}}{\partial p_t} = \frac{\partial x_{t1}}{\partial p_{i1}} = \frac{\partial x_{a1}}{\partial p_{i1}} = -\beta_c + \gamma_c$. Looking at the first FOC, changes in the price of rail p_t affect local demand q_t as well as demand for connecting passengers that combine rail and air, x_{t1} and x_{t2} . The total effect is negative since own effects dominate cross effects. Similarly, price changes in p_{i1} have an effect on demand for international travel as well as on demand for connecting passengers that combine train-air and air-air in the AB market; the total effect is negative. Eqs (16)-(17), together with $\frac{\partial \pi_a}{\partial p_a} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial \pi_{i2}}{\partial p_{i2}} = 0$ define a system of four equations and four unknowns that yield four equilibrium prices when there is competition. The equilibrium expressions are fairly complex. Thus, prices are a function of all per-passenger fees because of the network structure. To illustrate the changes in prices and show the role of per-passenger fees on the corresponding price differences under competition and cooperation, consider $a_l = a_i = 1$, $a_c = 2$, $b = 1$, $d_l = d_i = d_c = d$. For zero operating costs and the same airport fee at airports, f , the equilibrium prices are shown below:

$$p_t^* = \frac{(5+7d)(1-d)}{8+9d-5d^2} + f \Phi_t(d) + f_t \Psi_t(d), \quad (18)$$

$$p_a^* = \frac{(5+7d)(1-d)}{8+9d-5d^2} + f \Phi_a(d) + f_t \Psi_a(d), \quad (19)$$

$$p_i^* = p_{i1}^* = p_{i2}^* = \frac{(5+7d)(1-d)}{8+9d-5d^2} + f \Phi_i(d) + f_t \Psi_i(d). \quad (20)$$

In this manner, the equilibrium prices appear in terms of the degree of substitution (d), as well as the airport fee - multiplied by a polynomial in d , denoted by Φ_j , for $j = t, a, i$ - and the rail fee - also multiplied by a polynomial in d , with a similar notation as Ψ_j .⁷ The first thing to note is that per-passenger fees set by different infrastructure managers introduce asymmetries in prices per mode and link. In particular, $\frac{\partial p_t^*}{\partial f_t} > \frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial f_t} > 0$, where the latter expression is positive for $d > 0.3517$, and that $\frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial f} > \frac{\partial p_t^*}{\partial f} > 0$, so that rail fees have a positive and greater impact on rail price than on local air price in the *AH* market (and viceversa). Similarly, $\frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial f_t} > 0 > \frac{\partial p_i^*}{\partial f_t}$ and $\frac{\partial p_i^*}{\partial f} > \frac{\partial p_a^*}{\partial f} > 0$, meaning that asymmetric effects are induced by different per-passenger fees between the two types of air service operators. Finally, $\frac{\partial p_i^*}{\partial f} > 0 > \frac{\partial p_i^*}{\partial f_t}$, that clearly shows a negative effect of f_t versus a positive one of f on international air prices. In fact, the ordering of prices is $p_i^* > p_a^* > p_t^*$ when $f > f_t$; the opposite, otherwise.⁸ Note that, despite the fact that the local and the international airlines incur the same airport fees, we have that $p_i^* > p_a^*$. The reason for this is the complementarity relation of international airlines with the rail which does not happen between rail and the local airlines, and that allows international airlines to price higher than local airlines as a reaction to the lower rail prices when $f > f_t$. To sum up, the ordering of prices means that for symmetric demand conditions, prices for air trips are higher than for rail trips whenever airport fees exceed rail ones; this is true for links and for combined trips and, consequently, rail-air is cheaper than air-air in the *AB* market.

⁷The precise expressions of these polynomials appear in the Appendix.

⁸To obtain the ranking, note that $p_i^* - p_a^* = \frac{2(3+d)(1+2d)^2(1+3d)(f-f_t)}{(4+9d-d^2)(6+19d+11d^2)}$ and $p_a^* - p_t^* = \frac{2(3+d)(1+2d)(f-f_t)}{6+19d+11d^2}$, which are both positive for $f > f_t$.

3.2 The equilibrium under rail-air cooperation

Now we assume that the HSR operator and international airline 1 sign a cooperation agreement, which allows them to implement a mixed bundling pricing strategy. It consists of setting the component (link) prices p_t and p_{i1} that will be paid by passengers travelling AH by rail and flying HB with airline 1 or taking combinations as given by the composite goods or packages x_{t2} and x_{a1} . Furthermore, the allied operators will set a bundle price r_{t1} to those travellers willing to purchase the bundle x_{t1} . The above discussion implies that the joint profit function for the partners is given by,⁹

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{ti1} &= (p_t - c_t - 2f_t)(q_t + \bar{x}_{t2}) + (p_{i1} - c_a - f_B - f_H)(q_{i1} + \bar{x}_{a1}) \\ &\quad + (r_{t1} - c_t - c_a - 2f_t - f_H - f_B)\bar{x}_{t1};\end{aligned}\tag{21}$$

while for the transport operators that remain independent, profits are:

$$\pi_a = (p_a - c_a - f_A - f_H)(q_a + \bar{x}_{a1} + \bar{x}_{a2}),\tag{22}$$

$$\pi_{i2} = (p_{i2} - c_a - f_B - f_H)(q_{i2} + \bar{x}_{t2} + \bar{x}_{a2}).\tag{23}$$

Notice that the new system of demand equations for the connecting markets is given by,

$$\bar{x}_{t1}(r_{t1}, s_{t2}, s_{a1}, s_{a2}) = \alpha_c - \beta_c r_{t1} + \gamma_i(s_{t2} + s_{a1} + s_{a2}),\tag{24}$$

$$\bar{x}_{t2}(r_{t1}, s_{t2}, s_{a1}, s_{a2}) = \alpha_c - \beta_c s_{t2} + \gamma_i(r_{t1} + s_{a1} + s_{a2}),\tag{25}$$

$$\bar{x}_{a1}(r_{t1}, s_{t2}, s_{a1}, s_{a2}) = \alpha_c - \beta_c s_{a1} + \gamma_i(r_{t1} + s_{t2} + s_{a2}),\tag{26}$$

$$\bar{x}_{a2}(r_{t1}, s_{t2}, s_{a1}, s_{a2}) = \alpha_c - \beta_c s_{a2} + \gamma_i(r_{t1} + s_{t2} + s_{a1}).\tag{27}$$

Which implies that some marginal effects have changed as follows $\frac{\partial \bar{x}_{t2}}{\partial p_t} = \frac{\partial \bar{x}_{a1}}{\partial p_{i1}} = -\beta_c$ and therefore $|\frac{\partial \bar{x}_{t2}}{\partial p_t}| > |\frac{\partial x_{t2}}{\partial p_t}|$ and $|\frac{\partial \bar{x}_{a1}}{\partial p_{i1}}| > |\frac{\partial x_{a1}}{\partial p_{i1}}|$.

Now the first order conditions coming from the joint profit function are given

⁹To distinguish from the AB market system of demand equations in (8) to (11), we introduce the \bar{x}_k notation for $k = t1, t2, a1, a2$ when the bundle price r_{t1} is set by the firms that cooperate.

by:

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{ti1}}{\partial p_t} = (q_t + \bar{x}_{t2}) + (p_t - c_t - 2f_t) \left(\frac{\partial q_t}{\partial p_t} + \frac{\partial \bar{x}_{t2}}{\partial p_t} \right) \quad (28)$$

$$+ (p_{i1} - c_a - f_B - f_H) \frac{\partial \bar{x}_{a1}}{\partial p_t} + (r_{t1} - c_t - c_a - 2f_t - f_H - f_B) \frac{\partial \bar{x}_{t1}}{\partial p_t} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{ti1}}{\partial p_{i1}} = (q_{i1} + \bar{x}_{a1}) + (p_{i1} - c_a - f_B - f_H) \left(\frac{\partial q_{i1}}{\partial p_{i1}} + \frac{\partial \bar{x}_{a1}}{\partial p_{i1}} \right) \quad (29)$$

$$+ (p_t - c_t - 2f_t) \frac{\partial \bar{x}_{t2}}{\partial p_{i1}} + (r_{t1} - c_t - c_a - 2f_t - f_H - f_B) \frac{\partial \bar{x}_{t1}}{\partial p_{i1}} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{ti1}}{\partial r_{t1}} = \bar{x}_{t1} + (r_{t1} - c_t - c_a - 2f_t - f_H - f_B) \frac{\partial \bar{x}_{t1}}{\partial r_{t1}} \quad (30)$$

$$+ (p_t - c_t - 2f_t) \frac{\partial \bar{x}_{t2}}{\partial r_{t1}} + (p_{i1} - c_a - f_B - f_H) \frac{\partial \bar{x}_{a1}}{\partial r_{t1}} = 0.$$

Note that the partners in the agreement have *three* prices to set, instead of two under competition. Thus, by comparing (28) and (16) above regarding the marginal effect of p_t , we observe two additional effects. In the first one, the allied partners now internalize the competition that appears between their components through \bar{x}_{a1} . The second one captures the interplay between the component price, p_t , and demand for the bundle, \bar{x}_{t1} . An analogous argument applies for the marginal effect of p_{i1} . Finally, equation (29) includes the marginal effect of the bundle price on the demand of the combination fully controlled by the partners and the effect on the two combinations partially controlled, the mix-and-match combinations. The FOC for the operators that remain independent are as before, with the necessary changes brought by the new demand expressions in (24) to (27).

Under the symmetry assumed above, the equilibrium prices for partner operators are given by:

$$\bar{p}_t = \frac{(1-d)(16+71d+93d^2+36d^3)}{27+101d+2d^2(5-3d)(9+4d)} + f \bar{\Phi}_t(d) + f_t \bar{\Psi}_t(d), \quad (31)$$

$$\bar{p}_{i1} = \frac{(1-d)(16+71d+93d^2+36d^3)}{27+101d+2d^2(5-3d)(9+4d)} + f \bar{\Phi}_{i1}(d) + f_t \bar{\Psi}_{i1}(d), \quad (32)$$

$$\bar{r}_{t1} = \frac{(1-d)(27+113d+8d^2(17+6d))}{27+101d+2d^2(5-3d)(9+4d)} + f \bar{\Phi}_{t1}(d) + f_t \bar{\Psi}_{t1}(d). \quad (33)$$

Now, $\frac{\partial \bar{p}_t}{\partial f} > 0$ for $d > 0.4022$ and $\frac{\partial \bar{p}_{i1}}{\partial f_t} < 0$; the airport fee increases the price of rail travel for d large enough and the rail fee pushes down the component price of air travel in the international market. Besides, $\bar{p}_t + \bar{p}_{i1} > \bar{r}_{t1} > \bar{p}_t, \bar{p}_{i1}$ and so the non-arbitrage conditions hold.¹⁰

And the equilibrium prices for outsiders are:

$$\bar{p}_a = \frac{(1-d)(1+2d)(17+31d+12d^2)}{27+101d+2d^2(5-3d)(9+4d)} + f \bar{\Phi}_a(d) + f_t \bar{\Psi}_a(d), \quad (34)$$

$$\bar{p}_{i2} = \frac{(1-d)(1+2d)(17+31d+12d^2)}{27+101d+2d^2(5-3d)(9+4d)} + f \bar{\Phi}_{i2}(d) + f_t \bar{\Psi}_{i2}(d), \quad (35)$$

where now we again find that the rail fee pushes down the price of air travel in the international market, $\frac{\partial \bar{p}_{i2}}{\partial f_t} < 0$.

3.3 Effects of cooperation on prices

We now compare the equilibrium without and with rail-air cooperation. Comparisons are not clean so we shall report results for the symmetric case introduced above without and with per-passenger fees.

The next result provides the direction of price changes regarding prices per link.¹¹

Result 1 *Following rail-air cooperation, the changes of prices in the links are as follows:*

i) Without per-passenger fees, partners increase prices relative to the competition situation, $p_t^ = p_{i1}^* < \bar{p}_t = \bar{p}_{i1}$ for $0.15345 < d < 1$.*

Rail fees reduce the price difference of rail travel and increase the price difference on the air component price. Airport fees increase the rail travel difference for $d < 0.19395$ while they decrease the air component price difference.

ii) Without per-passenger fees, non-allied operators decrease prices relative to the competition situation, $\bar{p}_a = \bar{p}_{i2} < p_a^ = p_{i2}^*$ for $0.04206 < d < 1$.*

Rail fees exert a downwards pressure on the price difference of air travel in the international link and an upwards one on such difference in the local link. Airport fees reduce

¹⁰These conditions always hold when $f = f_t = 0$ and require a sufficiently large a in case infrastructure fees are positive.

¹¹Proofs are relegated to the Appendix.

the price difference of the air travel in the local link for all d and the same happens for the international link when $0.17730 < d < 0.72069$.

The literature has studied the effects of cooperation in complementary systems markets. Relevant references include Economides and Salop (1992), Beggs (1994), Choi (2008), and Flores-Fillol and Moner-Colonques (2011). The latter two papers contemplate that partner firms engage in mixed bundling, that is, they sell individual components (trips AH and HB) separately as well as selling the bundle (trip AB). Without the consideration of individual consumption, Choi (2008) shows that prices always increase; with individual consumption, Flores-Fillol and Moner-Colonques (2011) show that this holds as long as market sizes of individual and composite products are fairly similar. Our setting here assumes, in contrast with these papers, that each individual component (link) is supplied by two firms. Thus, market structure qualifies previous findings by establishing that partners increase prices and non-allied firms decrease them for some degree of product substitutability. Besides, the model allows us to highlight the role of per-passenger fees that are different per transport mode. The main conclusion from Result 1 is that fees can lessen or heighten the predictions of such price changes. It is also worth noting that, without fees, partners fix higher prices than non-allied operators for some degree of substitutability, $d \in (0.1187, 1)$. The consideration of fees implies that the price difference reduces because f and f_t diminish such difference. We may therefore conclude that per-passenger fees indeed influence the intensity of competition among transport operators.¹²

Regarding the changes in the AB trip prices, the following result can be proven.

Result 2 *The prices of AB trips change as follows:*

i) Without per-passenger fees, the price of the bundle under cooperation is lower than the

¹²The analysis, with the necessary changes, can naturally be conducted for an agreement between the domestic airline and an international airline. We would like to note that per-passenger fees may have different effects under air-air cooperation. Thus, part i) in Result 1 has rail fees always reducing the price differences. In part ii), rail fees exert a downward pressure on the price difference of rail travel; also on air travel for low enough d .

sum of prices under competition, $\bar{r}_{t1} < p_t^* + p_{i1}^* \forall d$. Per-passenger fees close such price difference.

ii) The bundle price is lower than non-allied operators' composite good: $\bar{r}_{t1} < \bar{p}_a + \bar{p}_{i2} \forall d$. Rail fees diminish while airport fees increase such difference.

iii) Without per-passenger fees, the bundle price is lower than mix-and-match ones: $\bar{r}_{t1} < \bar{p}_a + \bar{p}_{i1}, \bar{p}_t + \bar{p}_{i2} \forall d$. The price differences decrease with the rail fee f_t .

Under mixed bundling, Choi (2008) first suggested the price effects that arise following an agreement between producers of complementary goods. Partners reduce the price of the bundled system (and expand market share). They also increase the prices of components relative to the pre-agreement situation - in fact, they lose less than expected because of the bundle system price. This has the strategic consequence of increasing the prices of mix-and-match systems. Finally, independent operators respond by reducing the prices of their components to retain market share; however, such a decrease is not as large as the bundle price because they cannot internalize the complementarity externality. Similar conclusions are reached by Flores-Fillol and Moner-Colonques (2011), yet the direction of such price changes is true when the monopoly market for individual components is sufficiently large. The setting that we analyze has a duopolistic structure in each of the links AH and HB as well as four combinations to travel from A to B . When competition is strong (large enough d), partners internalize the pricing externality arising from the complementarity of the links (local and international trips) to reduce the price of the bundle AB - this is the well-known Cournot effect. From a strategic point of view, partners find it profitable to increase the prices of their individual links because, in this manner, combinations that include one of the components become less attractive to passengers. The response by independent rivals is no other than cutting their prices in an effort to retain some market share. However, when competition is weak (small enough d) partners prefer to decrease the prices of individual components and make mix-and-match systems more competitive.¹³

About 75% of the origin-destination routes in the US are operated by either a

¹³Part i) in Result 2 holds true under air-air cooperation. However, rail fees increase the gap

monopolist or by duopolists (see Tabacco, 2017 pp. 15-16). We may nevertheless make the following comments about the effect of more operators competing in each of the links. Note that when the number of operators competing in each link increases the number of combinations that connecting passengers can obtain increases geometrically, i.e. if there are n operators in markets AH and HB, then there will be n^2 possible combinations in the AB market. This implies that competition in the connecting markets increases by more. Thus, we expect component prices to fall. Note that each operator participates in $n + 1$ products and then by reducing its price it generates a positive effect, equal to the sum of the services offered in each of its products, and a negative effect, which is proportional to the margin. Since the second effect becomes more negative as n increases, a decrease in the equilibrium prices is expected. Cooperation would result in increases in the component prices set by partners and outsiders reacting by lowering their prices. Besides, the bundle price chosen by partners is lower than both mix-and-match and non-allied combinations (see Pardo-Garcia and Sempere-Monerris (2015) for a generalization to n components without individual consumption).

A final interesting consequence of cooperation between the operators of two links in a transport network is that it enhances connecting traffic, a common finding in the literature. In the simple model that we present this general result must be qualified. The next result provides a sufficient condition for rail-air cooperation to increase connecting consumer surplus.

Result 3 *Connecting traffic will increase as long as the price decrease of non-alliance operator's combination exceeds the price increase of the sum of individual components controlled by partners.*

Further results regarding total consumer surplus, industry profits, and welfare changes are difficult to establish. We resort to a numerical exercise with the purpose of providing insights on the impact of cooperation.

between the price of the combination offered by non-allied operators and the bundle price, and airport fees reduce such gap. Finally, part iii), the combination that entails rail travel becomes more expensive than the bundle as f_t increases, while it becomes cheaper as f decreases.

4 An empirical application

Once the formal analysis has been presented, the model is calibrated for the Spanish HSR services and local air services between Valencia-Madrid and from Madrid to an international destination, using the available data on elasticities, prices, traffic levels, and marginal operating costs. That is, we use the available data to construct compatible values for the unknown parameters of the model (subsection 4.1). We may subsequently simulate rail-air and air-air cooperation regarding industry profitability, consumer surplus and social welfare (subsection 4.2). A sensitivity analysis and the case of a network carrier appear in subsections 4.3 and 4.4, respectively. The empirical analysis abandons the symmetry assumed in the model in order to lend a more precise assessment of the effects brought about by cooperation.

4.1 Calibration

In a similar way to Álvarez et al. (2015, 2016) we use data available for the network and values for price elasticities in order to recover the parameters of the utility functions. In particular, the data for traffic volumes and prices are taken from statistics offered by AENA, the Spanish infrastructure manager, and RENFE, the Spanish passenger rail operator, and they are shown in Table 1. Valencia-Madrid is a route, initiated in December 2010, where HSR moved 2,100,000 passengers in the corridor, of which 1,785,000 were point to point traffic, and hardly 400,000 passengers used the air transport in 2016. There is an important presence of connecting passengers in the link Madrid-Valencia, especially about air users, which suppose a percentage close to 60%. As for the international destination, we will consider the city of New York since it shows high traffic levels from Madrid and no direct flight connects Valencia to New York.

Regarding elasticities, we have used the values appearing in some recent references (see Ortega-Hortelano et al., 2016, and IATA report, 2017). The results indicate that own-price elasticity is clearly higher for air transport (between 1.2 – 1.6) than elasticities for HSR (between 0.5 – 1). Although cross elasticities esti-

Table 1: Data for the Valencia-Madrid-New York network, year 2016.

Local air traffic (pass. per day and direction)	548
HSR traffic point to point (pass. per day and direction)	2,445
International air traffic (pass. per day and direction)	1,164
% of train connecting users local leg	30
% of air connecting users local leg	60
Local air price (€)	110
HSR price (€)	90
International air price (€)	600

Source: own elaboration

Table 2: Values for elasticities used in the calibration process.

	Own-price elasticity	Cross-price elasticity
HSR	-0.75	0.2
Air	-1.2	0.2

ated by the literature between air and train are usually relatively low, recent estimates have reported higher values for such cross elasticities (between 0.15 – 0.2), see Ortega-Hortelano et al., (2016).

With these data we define three equations with three unknowns, where parameters b_t , b_a , and d_l are obtained by using values of the traffic levels and prices and elasticities given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.¹⁴ These three equations are defined for the local train own-price elasticity, the air own-price elasticity and

¹⁴The utility functions considered here are i) the one appearing in (1) assuming different own effects for each mode as follows: $U_l = a_t q_t + a_a q_a - \frac{b_t}{2} q_t^2 - \frac{b_a}{2} q_a^2 - d_l q_t q_a$; ii) the one appearing in (3) as follows $U_c = a_{ct}(x_{t1} + x_{t2}) + a_{ca}(x_{a1} + x_{a2}) - \frac{b_t}{2}(x_{t1}^2 + x_{t2}^2) - \frac{b_a}{2}(x_{a1}^2 + x_{a2}^2) - d_c(x_{t1}x_{t2} + x_{t1}x_{a1} + x_{t1}x_{a2} + x_{t2}x_{a1} + x_{t2}x_{a2} + x_{a1}x_{a2})$ and where a_{ct} and a_{ca} correspond to the connecting passengers' maximum willingness to pay for a bundle including a HSR service in the first leg and that for a bundle including an air transport service in the first leg, respectively. Regarding the own effect in (2), b_a is assumed.

the cross-price elasticity in the local market. Parameter $d_i = 1.5d_l$, because the sensitivity in prices within the same air mode is higher than between different modes (train and air). Finally, parameter d_c in the utility function for connecting passengers is estimated as an average between d_l and d_i .

Now values for the willingness-to-pay constants in the utility functions are needed. To make the simulation more realistic, we include an additional utility equation for connecting users that, coming from elsewhere and not having HSR direct connections, use the hub airport (Madrid in our case) to take either airline 1 or 2 in the second leg of our model.¹⁵ Making use of the demand expressions, and from the levels of traffic and prices given in Table 1, we can recover the values for the willingness-to-pay constants. In particular, we use the demand equation for HSR in the local leg (as from the utility function i) given in footnote 14) to obtain a_t , similarly, the demand for the air services in the local leg to obtain a_a ; the demand of the international company 1 in the second leg (equation 6) to get a_i ; the demand for connecting train users (as from the utility function ii) given in footnote 14) to obtain a_{ct} , and the demand for the connecting air users to get a_{ca} .¹⁶ Finally, the demand for connecting users in the hub (obtained from the utility function defined in footnote 15) to get a_{ci} . Table 3 reports the values for all these parameters.

Next, values for costs must be set in the calibration. Data for operating train and air costs and for the infrastructure fees will be taken from a previous paper (see Álvarez et al, 2015). In that paper the values are defined by train or flight, and here they are divided by the number of seats weighted by an average load factor. We assume an average of 375 seats per train and 120 per local flight and around 85% of load factor. Finally, the operating costs for the international flight are taken

¹⁵The additional utility function reads, $U_{ci} = a_{ci}(q_{ci1} + q_{ci2}) - \frac{b_a}{2}(q_{ci1}^2 + q_{ci2}^2) - d_c q_{ci1} q_{ci2}$, where a_{ci} denotes the maximum willingness to pay for a traveler catching an international airline service in Madrid but coming from elsewhere. Note that those travelers have already spent some budget reaching Madrid from elsewhere, and we assume that the average price of such previous leg is equal to €80.

¹⁶To get the precise values of a_{ct} and a_{ca} , we have taken into account the connecting passengers coming from other Spanish cities where HSR connections are an option.

Table 3: Calibration of the utility functions parameters

	Willingness to pay		Own and cross effects
a_t	182.917	b_t	0.0455
a_a	158.093	b_a	0.0795
a_i	540.196	d_l	0.0146
a_{ct}	658.162	d_i	0.0219
a_{ca}	671.504	d_c	0.0182
a_{ci}	617.504		

Table 4: Operating and infrastructure costs per passenger

	Valencia- Madrid- New York
HSR costs	51.42
Air local costs	83.33
Air international costs	499.98
HSR infrastructure fee	4
Airport infrastructure fee	8

to be six times those of a local flight.¹⁷ Table 4 reports all the per passenger costs.

The results of the calibration process corresponding to the benchmark scenario, i.e. the competition case, are shown in the first column of Table 5. In the second column we assume that the HSR operator partners with one international air company (airline 1, for instance), and so it simulates the effects of rail-air cooperation. In the third column the partnership is established between the local air company and the international company 1, and so it simulates the effects of air-air cooperation. For the sake of the exposition, below each figure we set in

¹⁷Data for train operating costs are taken from Campos and de Rus (2009), air operating costs from Swan and Adler (2006), and infrastructure fees from the operators themselves.

italics and lower size a number indicating the percentage change with respect the results obtained in the competition case.

4.2 Discussion

In the case of rail-air cooperation we obtain that the bundle price offered by the partners is €616, which fulfills the arbitrage condition (joint price is lower than the sum of the individual prices). There is an increase of the HSR price by 4%, and a slight increase in the international air price of the allied company 1. However, prices for local air services and the non-allied international company 2 will slightly fall.

In terms of traffic, the most outstanding result is that connecting passengers using the partners' combination will rise by 89%, while connecting users traveling with the local air company and the partner's international leg will decrease by 33%. Additionally, regarding international traffic originated in Madrid there will be a rise by 24% in the traffic of non-allied company 2 at the expense of the company 1 decrease by 25%. A similar pattern is followed by connecting traffic reaching Madrid from elsewhere. To sum up, traffic increases happen in the markets that experience price decreases. In line with the predictions of the theoretical model, total Valencia-New York traffic will increase by 11.5% with cooperation.

Regarding profits, partners will increase their profits with respect to the sum of the profits obtained in the competition case by 5%, and the sum of profits for the local airline and company 2 will decrease by 18%. More interestingly, the results in terms of consumer surplus show that, as expected, users in the connecting market obtain a large gain of 36%, whereas consumer surplus of users in the local link falls by 8%. There are consumer gains in the international link by 4-6%. However, there is a net loss for the whole consumer surplus of just 0.5%. Industry profits increase by 2% finally resulting in a 0.8% welfare gain from rail-air cooperation.

In the third column we express the results when the collaboration is produced between the local air company and international company 1. The changes in prices follow a similar pattern to that in column two. The most notable result

is the large traffic increase (113%) in the number of connecting passengers travelling with the partners. In contrast with rail-air cooperation, the independent HSR operator sees its traffic increase by just 1%. The difference in the percentage changes under air-air cooperation are basically related with the fact that air traffic demand is more sensitive to price changes than rail traffic demand. Once again, total Valencia-New York traffic will increase by 7.7% with cooperation.

Note that air-air cooperation is profitable for partners (their profits are 26% higher than under competition), and there is a decrease in profits for the HSR and the air company 2 by 3% and 8%, respectively. It is worth noting that passengers in all markets are better off in consumer surplus terms, a finding in contrast with the received literature on airline alliances. We think this is due to the pricing strategies brought to light by cooperation in the current transport network and the sizes of the demand elasticities. Given that industry profits slightly increase by 0.4%, there is a final gain in social welfare by 2.2%.

One wonders which cooperation agreement, whether rail-air or air-air, is more likely to be implemented. The candidate agreement would be the one that generates the largest increase in profits for partners in the agreement. Denote by $\Delta_{ra,comp}$ the difference between the profits of the rail-air partners and the sum of the HSR operator and international airline 1 profits in the competition scenario, that is, $\Delta_{ra,comp} = 116,141 - (101,375 + 9,253) = \text{€}5,513$. Similarly, $\Delta_{aa,comp}$ is defined as the difference between the profits of the air-air partners and the sum of the local airline and international airline 1 profits in the competition scenario, that is, $\Delta_{aa,comp} = 21,724 - (7,932 + 9,253) = \text{€}4,539$. Therefore, the rail-air agreement is providing the largest increase in profits for partners. However, partners are asymmetric and side-payments may be required to ensure that the partners are willing to participate in a given cooperation agreement. Since international airline 1 is involved in the two agreements, let us assign to this company the role of deciding which one takes place. Our argument goes as follows. She will propose the agreement that maximizes her profits under the condition that each respective partner is getting at least what she can ensure by herself. The HSR operator has to receive at least €98,142, which is what she would earn were the

air-air agreement implemented, while the local airline has to receive no less than €7,208, the profits in case the rail-air agreement were implemented. Therefore, in this case, the rail-air agreement will be proposed. Finally, note that it would raise antitrust concerns since passenger surplus takes the lowest value.

4.3 Sensitivity analysis

The model developed in Section 3 unveils that per-passenger fees influence competition intensity among operators. In this subsection we will provide information about the effects of different per-passenger fee differences across modes in Table 6 and different levels of all per-passenger fees. The effects of alternative values of the cross-price elasticity are shown in Table 7.

i) The effect of changes in per-passenger fees

As a sensitivity test, we first study the impact of lowering per-passenger fees in one of the infrastructures keeping constant those of the other one on the distribution of welfare. Columns 1 to 3 in Table 6 report the reference point for sensitivity for the fee values considered above, that is, $f_t = 4$ and $f_A = f_H = 8$. Columns 4, 5 and 6, report results when there is a 25% decrease in rail fees. Column 4 corresponds to the competition scenario with the new reduced rail fee and it is the baseline in order to obtain percentage variations. By looking at columns 5 and 6 we observe that there are no qualitative differences of the effects of cooperation shown in columns 1 to 3. In comparison to the reference point, we observe that cooperation, whether rail-air or air-air, is slightly less profitable, passengers see lower reductions in welfare under rail-air cooperation whereas gains are less important in percentage variation under air-air cooperation. Finally, it is worth emphasizing that total welfare slightly increases under rail-air cooperation, whereas its gains are lower under air-air cooperation.

Next, columns 7, 8 and 9 present the results when airport fees are reduced by 25%. Column 7 corresponds to the competition scenario with the new reduced air fees. Columns 8 and 9 report similar qualitative changes to the reference point case. The only remarkable change to note is that the direct effect of lower air fees

is larger resulting in significant gains in passenger surplus (4.9%) and welfare (2.5%) under air-air cooperation. A general conclusion that follows is that lowering per-passenger fees does not affect the relative effects induced by cooperation agreements, and the level of profits, passenger surplus and total welfare increase as the per-passenger fees decrease.

Furthermore, we provide in Figure 2 the effect of rail fee changes in the range $[-25\%, 25\%]$ on $\Delta_{ra,comp}$ and $\Delta_{aa,comp}$. The same effects are reported in Figure 4 for the case of airport fees. Figures 3 and 5 report the passenger surplus levels for the two alternative agreements and the competition case when rail and airport fees change in the same range as above. They are denoted by PS_{aa} , PS_{ra} and PS_{comp} , respectively.

In Figure 2, we observe that the increase in profits for partners derived from the rail-air agreement is larger than the corresponding one for the air-air agreement and this order is kept for all values in the range; interestingly, both differences get closer as the rail fee increases. Figure 4 shows the same ordering as Figure 2 when airport fees vary in the same range, but $\Delta_{ra,comp}$ and $\Delta_{aa,comp}$ separate from one another as airport fees increase. In Figure 3 we observe that all passenger surplus levels decrease with f_t and that the passenger surplus corresponding to the air-air agreement is the largest, the second largest is the one corresponding to the competition scenario. In Figure 5 the same pattern applies.

We have also undertaken simulations on how results vary when all the per-passenger fees vary in the range $[-50\%, 50\%]$ on the calibration levels and keeping the same relative differences between them, that is f_t is half the size of f_A and f_H . We find that both $\Delta_{ra,comp}$ and $\Delta_{aa,comp}$ decrease as fee levels increase and run apart noting that $\Delta_{ra,comp}$ is always larger than $\Delta_{aa,comp}$. Passenger surplus levels decrease with the fee levels, the passenger surplus corresponding to the air-air agreement is again the largest, but the second largest is the one corresponding to the competition scenario as long as $f_t > 2.66$ ($f_A = f_H > 5.32$). Then, both cooperation agreements increase passenger surplus when the infrastructure fees are low enough. Finally, computing the infrastructure fee elasticity of the respective passenger surplus around the calibration values ($f_t = 4, f_A = f_H = 8$), we find

that a 1% decrease in all fees will increase passenger surplus in the competition scenario by 0.227%, that of the air-rail agreement by 0.244% and that of the air-air agreement by 0.235%.

ii) The effect of changes in the cross-price elasticity

We provide, in Table 7, the sensitivity analysis for two different values of the cross elasticity between HSR and the local airline services. In columns 1 to 3 we present the distribution of profits across operators, passenger surplus, industry profits and social welfare for the competition scenario, the rail-air agreement and the air-air agreement, respectively, for the case of a lower cross elasticity value, that is 0.1. Columns 4 to 6, reproduce the figures for our baseline case, i.e. when the cross elasticity is 0.2. Finally, columns 7 to 9 consider the case of a larger cross elasticity value, that is 0.3. Note that a change in the cross elasticity implies a re-calibration of all the utility function parameters, that is, all a 's, b 's, and d 's inducing complex changes among the variables. Passenger surplus, industry profits and total welfare increase as the cross elasticity does, for a given scenario. In case of lower cross elasticity, we observe that the relative gains in total welfare, industry profits and passenger induced by cooperation are larger. In this case the rail-air agreement increases passenger surplus in contrast to what happens in the baseline case. Regarding the effect of cooperation in the distribution of profits across operators, a lower cross elasticity value does not imply any significant qualitative changes. Finally, in the case of larger cross elasticity the only qualitative difference with respect to the baseline case is that the rail-air cooperation leads to a welfare reduction. Regarding the incentives to implement a given agreement, both $\Delta_{ra,comp}$ and $\Delta_{aa,comp}$ increase with the cross elasticity and the former is always larger than the latter. The rail-air agreement is the one proposed and again is the one that generates the lowest passenger surplus of the two agreements.

4.4 The network carrier analysis

There are examples where the local airline also serves the international market, i.e. a network carrier serves fully the AB market. Therefore, as a robustness exercise, we provide a simulation analysis (Table 8) where the starting point is asymmetric, that is, there is a network carrier competing with a HSR service in the AH market and with another international airline in the HB market. Next, we simulate two alternative agreements including the HSR operator as a partner. One formed by the HSR operator and the remaining international airline, the *rail-air agreement*, and another one, where the HSR operator and the network carrier become partners, the *rail-network carrier agreement*. Note that both agreements are quite different in strategic terms. The rail-network carrier agreement is exacerbating the initial asymmetry in the network as the partners monopolize the AH market (a horizontal agreement type) and compete with a firm only offers one service in the HB market; in contrast, the rail-air agreement restores symmetry since both competitors internalize the complementarities derived from serving the AB market and compete also by offering a full service in the AB market. Such qualitative differences are shown in the analysis as follows. Under the rail-network carrier agreement, there are two bundle services fully controlled by the partners - the price of trip AB by the network carrier and the price of the that trip by combining rail and air with the network carrier - apart from the corresponding component prices; while the remaining operator, the international airline 2, only sets one component price. Under the rail-air agreement, each competitor is fully controlling one bundle. We present the results of the simulations in Table 8.

Regarding component prices, both agreements increase the rail price since the HSR firm is involved in both cooperation agreement types and it increases by more with the rail-network carrier agreement, in particular by 9.8% as compared to 4.1% with the rail-air agreement. The component prices set by the network carrier are realigned depending on the agreement considered. The rail-air agreement leads to a slight decrease in the local air price and an increase in the international air price. In contrast, the rail-network carrier agreement increases the local air price by 9.9% while it barely reduces the international air price by 0.5%. Fi-

nally, the international price of airline 2 barely decreases whenever an agreement takes place. Finally, regarding the bundle prices, the rail-air agreement pushes the network carrier to set a lower bundle price showing the effect of increased bundle competition. However, the rail-network carrier agreement leads to a higher (1.9%) bundle price. In fact, the prices of the combined trips are the highest when the rail-network carrier agreement is at work.

The effects on prices mentioned above translate to passengers surplus as follows: passengers in the local market (AH market) are worse off as their surplus is reduced by 8.5% and 22.9% under the rail-air and the rail-network carrier agreements, respectively. However, passengers in the international market are better off under either agreement, whose gains are larger under the rail-network carrier agreement (their surplus is increased by 43.7%). It is worth noting that local connecting passengers, which are always benefited by cooperation, experience an important fall in their surplus (23%) when the rail-network carrier agreement takes place. The cooperation agreement that generates a higher increase in partner profits is the rail-network carrier agreement leading to a 9.3% increase as compared to a 5.3% increase in the case of the rail-air agreement. The non-allied operators see a reduction in profits, by 15.8% for the network carrier in the case of the rail-air agreement and by 70% for airline 2 in the case of the rail-network carrier agreement.

Finally, regarding total passenger surplus, industry profits and total welfare, note that the implementation of the rail-network carrier agreement reduces total passenger surplus by much more, 19.8% as compared to 0.6% decrease in the case of a rail-air agreement; while the rail-network carrier agreement increases industry profits by more, 4.1% compared to 1.8% in the case of a rail-air agreement. Total welfare, slightly increases when the rail-air agreement is implemented, notably decreasing by 6.5%, otherwise.¹⁸

¹⁸The papers by Socorro and Vicens (2013), Jiang and Zhang (2014) and Avenali et al. (2018) have considered the case studied in this subsection where the same airline serves both the local and the international markets. Note however that our results are not directly comparable with the former two references. Thus, Socorro and Vicens (2013) and Jiang and Zhang (2014) assume that, under competition, the trip AB can only be made by air and, under cooperation, Socorro

5 Conclusions

This paper has presented a model of competition between HSR and air modes in a transport network. With cooperation, partner operators decrease the bundle price. For a high enough degree of product differentiation, partner operators find it strategically advantageous to raise the prices per link, thus making substitute "mix-and-match" combinations less attractive to users. Non-allied operators respond by decreasing the prices per link. It is shown that cooperation is beneficial for connecting passengers that travel from A to B . Formally, the model unveils distinctive effects of per-passenger fees that are different for rail and for air travel. Whether cooperation raises consumer surplus and welfare is assessed by calibrating the model. Besides, this allows us to consider a more realistic scenario by exploiting asymmetries per mode and market. The empirical application shows that cooperation is profitable for partners, yet welfare gains happen to be higher under air-air cooperation relative to rail-air cooperation, although the latter is more likely to be formed. Total passenger surplus typically falls, which would raise antitrust concerns. Our analysis emphasizes the relevance of the levels of per-passenger fees. Welfare gains, in percentage terms, happen to be higher when fees are lower and also for lower values of cross-price elasticity between modes.

The model can be employed to perform various simulation exercises, which should be helpful in the design of transport policies. In particular, those analyses would provide insights as to the impact of rail-air cooperation in transport networks, a type of cooperation that is becoming more popular, as noted in the introduction. Rail-air cooperation produces increases in total traffic and a reallocation of traffic from air to train transport. Our analysis has disregarded any benefits

and Viécens (2013) consider that HSR takes all demand in the local market and operates as a monopolist. Avenali et al. (2018) allow for all combinations and assume quantity competition. These authors analyze a capacity purchase agreement and a joint venture agreement. The latter means that the network carrier and the HSR operator create a distinct business unit in charge of the combined rail-air trip. These authors shows that consumer surplus and welfare are higher under the agreement, which is in contrast with our findings in column three, basically because of the monopolization effect that arises under the cooperation agreement that we consider.

in the form of easier connections, increases in the frequency of service, schedule coordination, and so on. This basically means that, from a demand perspective, the impact of rail-air cooperation is underestimated. The same argument applies in terms of costs since any potential efficiency gains have not been taken into account. Therefore, our setting suggests positive welfare effects when the consequences of cooperation are guided just by the pricing strategies of partners. The results obtained are an invitation to pursue further research on the quantification of intermodal collaborations that may permit informed policy measures, such as the construction of new transport infrastructures and the choice of access fees per transport mode.

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Appendix: Expressions and proofs

We first provide the expressions corresponding to the effects of f and f_t on equilibrium prices for the competition case. That is,

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_t(d) &= \frac{2(5-d)(3+d)(1+2d)^2}{(4+9d-d^2)(8+9d-5d^2)} - \frac{2(1+3d)(3+d)(1+2d)^2}{(4+9d-d^2)(6+19d+11d^2)} - \frac{2(3+d)(1+2d)}{(6+19d+11d^2)} > 0 \\ &\text{for } d > 0.3517 \\ \Psi_t(d) &= \frac{2(1+3d)(3+d)(1+2d)^2}{(4+9d-d^2)(6+19d+11d^2)} - \frac{2(1-d^2)(3+d)(1+2d)}{(4+9d-d^2)(8+9d-5d^2)} > 0 \\ \Phi_a(d) &= \frac{2(5-d)(3+d)(1+2d)^2}{(4+9d-d^2)(8+9d-5d^2)} - \frac{2(1+3d)(3+d)(1+2d)^2}{(4+9d-d^2)(6+19d+11d^2)} > 0 \\ \Psi_a(d) &= \frac{2(1+3d)(3+d)(1+2d)^2}{(4+9d-d^2)(6+19d+11d^2)} - \frac{2(1-d^2)(3+d)(1+2d)}{(4+9d-d^2)(8+9d-5d^2)} + \frac{2(3+d)(1+2d)}{(6+19d+11d^2)} > 0 \\ \Phi_i(d) &= \frac{2(5-d)(3+d)(1+2d)^2}{(4+9d-d^2)(8+9d-5d^2)} > 0 \\ \Psi_i(d) &= -\frac{2(1-d^2)(3+d)(1+2d)}{(4+9d-d^2)(8+9d-5d^2)} < 0\end{aligned}$$

It is easily shown that: $\Phi_i(d) > \Phi_a(d) > \Phi_t(d)$ and $\Psi_t(d) > \Psi_a(d) > 0 > \Psi_i(d)$. Also, $\Phi_i(d) > 0 > \Psi_i(d)$, $\Psi_t(d) > \Phi_t(d)$ and $\Phi_a(d) > \Psi_a(d)$.

Similarly, the expressions corresponding to the effects of f and f_t on equilibrium prices for the rail-air cooperation case are:

a) for the prices set by the partners in the cooperative agreement,

$$\bar{\Phi}_{t1}(d) = \frac{27 + 134d + 211d^2 + 4d^3(25 + 2d)}{27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d)} > 0$$

$$\bar{\Psi}_{t1}(d) = \frac{27 + 98d + 103d^2 + 4d^3(5 - 2d)}{27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d)} > 0$$

$$\bar{\Phi}_{i1}(d) = \bar{\Phi}_{t1}(d) - \frac{91 + 911d + 3239d^2 + 4917d^3 + 2914d^4 + 532d^5 + 212d^6 + 144d^7}{(19 + 59d + 32d^2 - 2d^3)(27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d))} > 0$$

$$\bar{\Psi}_{i1}(d) = \bar{\Psi}_{t1}(d) - \frac{(1 + 2d)(517 + 2603d + 4221d^2 + 2205d^3 - 358d^4 - 500d^5 - 48d^6)}{(19 + 59d + 32d^2 - 2d^3)(27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d))} < 0$$

$$\bar{\Phi}_t(d) = \bar{\Phi}_{i1}(d) - \frac{2(2 + d)(5 + 14d + 5d^2)}{19 + 59d + 32d^2 - 2d^3} > 0 \text{ for } d > 0.4022$$

$$\bar{\Psi}_t(\gamma) = \bar{\Psi}_{i1}(d) + \frac{2(2 + d)(5 + 14d + 5d^2)}{19 + 59d + 32d^2 - 2d^3} > 0$$

It is easily shown that: $\bar{\Phi}_{t1}(d) > \bar{\Phi}_{i1}(d) > \bar{\Phi}_t(d)$ and $\bar{\Psi}_t(d) > \bar{\Psi}_{t1}(d) > 0 > \bar{\Psi}_{i1}(d)$.

It also holds that: $\bar{\Psi}_t(d) > \bar{\Phi}_t(d)$, $\bar{\Phi}_{i1}(d) > 0 > \bar{\Psi}_{i1}(d)$ and $\bar{\Phi}_{t1}(d) > \bar{\Psi}_{t1}(d)$.

b) for the prices set by the operators not in the cooperative agreement,

$$\bar{\Phi}_{i2}(d) = \frac{2(236 + 1839d + 5392d^2 + 7303d^3 + 4380d^4 + 656d^5 - 294d^6 - 72d^7)}{(19 + 59d + 32d^2 - 2d^3)(27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d))} > 0$$

$$\bar{\Psi}_{i2}(d) = -\frac{4(1 - d)(1 + d)^2(23 + 98d + 128d^2 + 75d^3 + 36d^4)}{(19 + 59d + 32d^2 - 2d^3)(27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d))} < 0$$

$$\bar{\Phi}_a(\gamma) = \bar{\Phi}_{i2}(d) + \frac{4(2 + 3d)(3 + d)(1 + 2d)}{27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d)} > 0$$

$$\bar{\Psi}_a(\gamma) = \bar{\Psi}_{i2}(d) + \frac{2(1 + 3d)(2 + d)(1 + 2d)}{19 + 59d + 32d^2 - 2d^3} > 0$$

Finally: $\bar{\Phi}_{i2}(\gamma) > \bar{\Phi}_a(\gamma) > \bar{\Psi}_a(\gamma) > 0 > \bar{\Psi}_{i2}(\gamma)$

Proof of Result 1

For part i), considering $f_t = f = 0$, the differences $\bar{p}_t - p_t^*$ and $\bar{p}_{i1} - p_{i1}^*$ are positive iff $-7 + 25d + 121d^2 + 89d^3 - 12d^4 > 0$, or equivalently for $0.15345 < d < 1$.

Regarding the effects of positive fees, we have:

$$\frac{\partial(\bar{p}_t - p_t^*)}{\partial f} = \bar{\Phi}_t(d) - \Phi_t(d) < 0 \text{ for } d > 0.19395, \quad (36)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\bar{p}_t - p_t^*)}{\partial f_t} = \bar{\Psi}_t(d) - \Psi_t(d) < 0 \forall d, \quad (37)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\bar{p}_{i1} - p_{i1}^*)}{\partial f} = \bar{\Phi}_{i1}(d) - \Phi_{i1}(d) < 0 \forall d, \quad (38)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\bar{p}_{i1} - p_{i1}^*)}{\partial f_t} = \bar{\Psi}_{i1}(d) - \Psi_{i1}(d) > 0 \forall d. \quad (39)$$

For part ii), considering $f_t = f = 0$, the differences $p_a^* - \bar{p}_a$ and $p_{i2}^* - \bar{p}_{i2}$ are positive iff $(-1 + 21d + 64d^2 + 48d^3) > 0$, or equivalently for $0.04206 < d < 1$.

Regarding the effects of positive fees, we have:

$$\frac{\partial(p_a^* - \bar{p}_a)}{\partial f} = \Phi_a(d) - \bar{\Phi}_a(d) < 0 \forall d, \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{\partial(p_a^* - \bar{p}_a)}{\partial f_t} = \Psi_a(d) - \bar{\Psi}_a(d) > 0 \forall d, \quad (41)$$

$$\frac{\partial(p_{i2}^* - \bar{p}_{i2})}{\partial f} = \Phi_{i2}(d) - \bar{\Phi}_{i2}(d) < 0 \text{ for } 0.17730 < d < 0.72069, \quad (42)$$

$$\frac{\partial(p_{i2}^* - \bar{p}_{i2})}{\partial f_t} = \Psi_{i2}(d) - \bar{\Psi}_{i2}(d) < 0 \forall d. \quad (43)$$

Proof of Result 2

Part i) refers to the difference $(p_i^* + p_{i1}^* - \bar{r}_{i1})$, which for $f = f_t = 0$, equals:

$$\frac{a(1-d)(54 + 241d + 344d^2 + 77d^3 - 188d^4 - 96d^5)}{(8 + 9d - 5d^2)(27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d))},$$

and it is positive.

Regarding the effect of f_t on the difference $(p_t^* + p_{i1}^* - \bar{r}_{t1})$, it happens that the derivative of such difference with respect to f_t reads,

$$\frac{(1-d)(486 + 3672d + 10583d^2 + 13559d^3 + 4715d^4 - 5803d^5 - 5668d^6 - 1384d^7)}{(6 + 19d + 11d^2)(8 + 9d - 5d^2)(27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d))},$$

and it is negative.

Similarly, the derivative of such difference with respect to f reads,

$$\frac{(1-d)(162 + 1272d + 3891d^2 + 5739d^3 + 3523d^4 - 799d^5 - 2116d^6 - 728d^7)}{(6 + 19d + 11d^2)(8 + 9d - 5d^2)(27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d))},$$

and it is negative, too. Therefore, $(p_t^* + p_{i1}^* - \bar{r}_{t1}) > 0$ for $f = f_t = 0$, and that difference decreases for larger fees.

Part ii) refers to the difference $(\bar{p}_a + \bar{p}_{i2} - \bar{r}_{t1})$, which for $f = f_t = 0$, equals:

$$\frac{a(1-d)(7 + 17d + 12d^2)}{(27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d))},$$

and it is positive.

The effect of f_t on the difference $(\bar{p}_a + \bar{p}_{i2} - \bar{r}_{t1})$ is negative and reads:

$$\frac{(31 + 84d + 41d^2 - 28d^3 - 8d^4)}{27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d)},$$

while that of f is positive and equal to:

$$\frac{(1+d)(17 + 47d + 4d^2 - 8d^3)}{27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d)},$$

Part iii) refers to the differences $(\bar{p}_a + \bar{p}_{i1} - \bar{r}_{t1})$, and $(\bar{p}_t + \bar{p}_{i2} - \bar{r}_{t1})$ which for $f = f_t = 0$, equals:

$$\frac{a(1-d)(6 + 23d + 31d^2 + 12d^4)}{27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d)},$$

and it is positive.

The effect of f_t on the difference $(\bar{p}_a + \bar{p}_{i1} - \bar{r}_{t1})$, is positive and reads:

$$\frac{(1+d)(273 + 1496d + 2549d^2 + 1458d^3 + 520d^4 + 144d^5)}{(19 + 59d + 32d^2 - 2d^3)(27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d))},$$

while that of f is negative and equal to:

$$-\frac{(501 + 3123d + 6739d^2 + 5293d^3 - 276d^4 - 1960d^5 - 508d^6 - 48d^7)}{(19 + 59d + 32d^2 - 2d^3)(27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d))},$$

The effect of f_t on the difference $(\bar{p}_t + \bar{p}_{i2} - \bar{r}_{t1})$ is negative and reads:

$$-\frac{(1 - d)(69 + 388d + 865d^2 + 1062d^3 + 722d^4 + 200d^5)}{(19 + 59d + 32d^2 - 2d^3)(27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d))},$$

and that of f is also negative and equal to:

$$-\frac{2(53 + 345d + 739d^2 + 363d^3 - 640d^4 - 712d^5 - 164d^6 + 16d^7)}{(19 + 59d + 32d^2 - 2d^3)(27 + 101d + 2d^2(5 - 3d)(9 + 4d))}.$$

Proof of Result 3

First note that consumer surplus for the connecting market is defined as $CS_c = U_c - \sum_{\forall l} s_l x_l$ for $l = t1, t2, a1, a2$. This expression is increasing with total connecting traffic. Then, we are interested in finding a sufficient condition that ensures an increase in total connecting traffic when cooperation rail-air arises.

Following expressions (8) to (11), $\sum_{\forall l} x_l = 4\alpha_c - (\beta_c - 3\gamma_c) \sum_{\forall l} s_l$; similarly for the rail-air cooperation connecting demands: $\sum_{\forall l} \bar{x}_l = 4\alpha_c - (\beta_c - 3\gamma_c)(r_{t1} + s_{t2} + s_{a1} + s_{a2})$. It follows that

$$\sum_{\forall l} \bar{x}_l > \sum_{\forall l} x_l \text{ iff } 2(p_t^* + p_a^* + p_{i1}^* + p_{i2}^*) > 2(\bar{p}_{i2} + \bar{p}_a) + \bar{r}_{t1} + \bar{p}_{i1} + \bar{p}_t.$$

Reorganizing the last expression, the condition becomes:

$$2(p_a^* + p_{i2}^* - (\bar{p}_a + \bar{p}_{i2})) > (\bar{r}_{t1} - (p_t^* + p_{i1}^*)) + (\bar{p}_t + \bar{p}_{i1} - (p_t^* + p_{i1}^*)).$$

Finally, it follows that for the above condition to be satisfied, it suffices that:

$$(p_a^* + p_{i2}^* - (\bar{p}_a + \bar{p}_{i2})) > (\bar{p}_t + \bar{p}_{i1} - (p_t^* + p_{i1}^*)).$$

For the conditions on d under which $(\bar{r}_{t1} - (p_t^* + p_{i1}^*)) < 0$, $(p_a^* + p_{i2}^* - (\bar{p}_a + \bar{p}_{i2})) > 0$ and $(\bar{p}_t + \bar{p}_{i1} - (p_t^* + p_{i1}^*)) > 0$.

Table 5. The effects of cooperation in the Valencia-Madrid-New York network.

	Competition	Rail-air	Air-air
HSR price (p_t)	99.4	103.4	98.8
		4.01%	-0.64%
Local air price (p_a)	113.6	112.9	114.8
		-0.58%	1.15%
Intern. air price 1 (p_{i1})	528.2	529.9	528.6
		0.32%	0.09%
Intern. air price 2 (p_{i2})	528.2	526.5	527.7
		-0.33%	-0.10%
Rail-air bundle price (r_{t1})		616.0	
Air-air bundle price (r_{a1})			629.1
Local train passeng. (q_t)	1758	1662	1778
		-5.46%	1.14%
Connect. train passeng. (x_{t1})	387	730	338
		88.63%	-12.66%
Connect. train passeng. (x_{t2})	387	221	375
		-42.89%	-3.10%
Local air passengers (q_a)	238	264	218
		10.92%	-8.40%
Connect. passeng. airl. 1 (x_{a1})	160	107	342
		-33.13%	113.75%
Connect. passeng. airl. 2 (x_{a2})	160	162	123
		1.25%	-23.13%
Intern. air passeng. airl. 1 (q_{i1})	119	89	110
		-25.21%	-7.56%
Intern. air passeng. airl. 2 (q_{i2})	119	148	127
		24.37%	6.72%
Intern. connecting airl. 1 (q_{ci1})	94	66	86
		-29.79%	-8.51%
Intern. connecting airl. 2 (q_{ci2})	94	122	102
		29.79%	8.51%

Table 5: Continued

	Competition	Rail-air	Air-air
HSR profits	101375		98142
			-3.19%
Local airline profits	7932	7208	
		-9.13%	
Intern. airline 1 profits	9253		
Intern. airline 2 profits	9253	6832	8472
		-26.16%	-8.44%
Profits rail-air partners		116141	
Profits air-air partners			21724
Passeng. Surplus (local users)	78649	72006	79488
		-8.45%	1.07%
Passeng. Surplus (intern. users)	1424	1476	1436
		3.65%	0.84%
Passeng. Surplus (local connect.)	16593	22632	20172
		36.39%	21.57%
Passeng. Surplus (intern. connect.)	861	909	870
		5.57%	1.05%
Total Passenger Surplus	97527	97023	101966
		-0.52%	4.55%
Industry profits	127813	130181	128338
		1.85%	0.41%
Total welfare	225340	227204	230304
		0.83%	2.20%

Table 6. Sensitivity analysis under changes in per passenger fees

	$f_t = 4; f_H = f_A = 8$			$\downarrow f_t = 25\%$			$\downarrow f_A = \downarrow f_H = 25\%$		
	Compet.	Rail-air	Air-air	Compet.	Rail-air	Air-air	Compet.	Rail-air	Air-air
HSR & int. airline 1 sum of profits	110628	116141		115609	121196		111707	117443	
		4.98%			4.83%			4.96%	
Profits HSR	101375		98142	106128		102778	101087		97850
			-3.19%			-3.16%			-3.05%
Profits Airline 1	9253			9481			10620		
Profits Local airline	7932	7208		7620	6921		10512	9604	
		-9.13%			-9.17%			-11.92%	
Local airl. & int. airl. 1 sum of profits	17185		21724	17101		21610	21132		26174
			26.41%			26.37%			29.48%
Profits Airline 2	9253	6832	8472	9481	7000	8689	10620	7995	9746
		-26.16%	-8.44%		-26.17%	-8.35%		-27.69%	-9.22%
Passenger surplus	97527	97023	101966	100201	99842	104636	100566	100284	105474
		-0.52%	4.55%		-0.36%	4.43%		-0.28%	4.88%
Industry profits	127813	130181	128338	132710	135117	133077	132839	135042	133770
		1.85%	0.41%		1.81%	0.28%		1.66%	0.70%
Total welfare	225340	227204	230304	232911	234959	237713	233405	235326	239244
		0.83%	2.20%		0.88%	2.06%		0.82%	2.50%

Figure 2: Sensitivity in f_t . Changes in the profits increase for partners.

Figure 3 : Sensitivity in f_t . Changes in passenger surplus.

Figure 4: Sensitivity in f_A and f_H . Changes in the profits increase for partners.

Figure 5: Sensitivity in f_A and f_H . Changes in passenger surplus.

Table 7. Cross elasticity sensitivity analysis

	Cross elasticity = 0.1			Cross elasticity = 0.2			Cross elasticity = 0.3		
	Compet.	Rail-air	Air-air	Compet.	Rail-air	Air-air	Compet.	Rail-air	Air-air
HSR & int. airline 1 sum of profits	109180	115670		110628	116141		113559	118484	
		5.94%			4.98%			4.34%	
Profits HSR	98539		96741	101375		98142	104745		100275
			-1.82%			-3.19%			-4.27%
Profits Airline 1	10641			9253			8814		
Profits Local airline	7111	6832		7932	7208		8677	7603	
		-3.92%						-12.38%	
Local airt. & int. airt. 1 sum of profits	17752		22590	17185		21724	17491		21900
			27.25%			26.41%			25.21%
Profits Airline 2	10641	8447	10174	9253	6832	8472	8814	6226	7879
		-20.62%	-4.39%		-26.16%	-8.44%		-29.36%	-10.61%
Passenger surplus	82408	83080	86800	97527	97023	101966	125316	123597	129661
		0.82%	5.33%		-0.52%	4.55%		-1.37%	3.47%
Industry profits	126932	130949	129505	127813	130181	128338	131050	132313	130054
		3.16%	2.03%		1.85%	0.41%		0.96%	-0.76%
Total welfare	209340	214029	216305	225340	227204	230304	256366	255910	259715
		2.24%	3.33%		0.83%	2.20%		-0.18%	1.31%

Table 8. Cooperation for the case of a network carrier

	Competition	Rail-air	Rail-network carrier
HSR price (p_t)	98.8	102.8	108.5
		4.07%	9.81%
Local air price (p_a)	114.8	113.9	126.2
		-0.84%	9.85%
Intern. air price 1 (p_{i1})	528.6	529.4	525.7
		0.14%	-0.55%
Intern. air price 2 (p_{i2})	527.7	526.7	525.7
		-0.17%	-0.36%
Rail-air bundle price		615.1	621.6
Air-air bundle price	629.1	627.6	640.9
		-0.23%	1.89%
HSR profits	98142		
Intern. airline 2 profits	8472		2544
			-69.97%
Network carrier profits	21724	18291	
		-15.80%	
Profits rail-air partners		112314	
Profits rail-network carrier partners			130993
Passeng. Surplus (local users)	79488	72757	61269
		-8.47%	-22.92%
Passeng. Surplus (intern. users)	1436	1482	2063
		3.20%	43.66%
Passeng. Surplus (local connect.)	20172	26180	17077
		29.78%	-15.34%
Passeng. Surplus (intern. connect.)	870	910	1381
		4.60%	58.74%
Total Passenger Surplus	101966	101329	81790
		-0.62%	-19.79%
Industry profits	128338	130605	133537
		1.77%	4.05%
Total welfare	230304	231934	215327
		0.71%	-6.50%